

SYMBOLIC COMPUTATION APPLIED TO FUNCTION FACTORIZATION CONCEPT: THE RATIONAL SCALAR CASE

Ana C. Conceição^{1,2}, Jéssica C. Pires³ and Celestino Coelho¹

1: Faculdade de Ciências e Tecnologia, Universidade do Algarve
Campus de Gambelas, 8005-139 Faro, Portugal
e-mail:aconcei@ualg.pt

2: Center for Research & Development in Mathematics and Applications
Campus Universitário de Santiago, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

3: Faculdade de Economia, Universidade do Algarve
Campus de Gambelas, 8005-139 Faro, Portugal
e-mail: {aconcei,jccpires,ccoelho}@ualg.pt

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Abstract. *Operator theory has many applications in several main scientific research areas such as structural mechanics, aeronautics, quantum mechanics, probability theory, electrical engineering, among others. Factorization theory is closely related to the computation of singular integrals. Some progress has been achieved for some classes of functions whose properties allow the use of a particular strategy in the study of the factorization problem, but there is no general method for obtaining a factorization for a given function. In our work, we design and develop operator theory algorithms. By implementing these algorithms on a computer, using the numeric and symbolic computation capabilities of the Wolfram Mathematica computer algebra system, new tools are created, making the results of lengthy and complex calculations available in a simple way to researchers of different areas. The main goal of this talk is to present new rational factorization algorithms, which have applications in the study of the invertibility of singular integral operators and in the computation of the kernel of certain classes of operators. Several nontrivial examples computed with the algorithms are presented.*

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1 INTRODUCTION

The factorization theory of matrix functions has a rich history dating back to Plemelj's work in 1908. It has been developed to solve problems arising from various fields in mathematics and physics. Currently, the theory has a wide range of applications, including the study of Riemann-Hilbert boundary value problems, Fredholm theory of singular integral operators, and non-linear and linear differential equations, diffraction of acoustic and electromagnetic waves, scattering theory, inverse scattering theory, and some branches of probability theory [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8]. For some classes of functions there has been some progress by the use of specific strategies to study the factorization problem, but there is no general and explicit method to find a factorization for a given function. Additionally, existing algorithms only demonstrate that some factorization is possible, but they are not suitable for computer implementation [9, 10]. Regarding partial indices, some advances have been made, but the methods are difficult to apply and not designed for computer implementation, even in the rational case [11, 12, 13]. Most of the explicit analytical factorization methods rely on finding the roots of scalar functions. Therefore, in many real-world applications, numerical analysis of such methods is unavoidable. However, the numerical approach to factorization theory is very challenging due to many instability issues, such as those affecting the factorization indices [5]. For this reason, the development of new analytical methods, even if only for some special classes of functions, remains crucial for the progress of this theory.

On the other hand, computer algebra systems (CAS) with extensive capabilities of numeric and symbolic computation have become accessible to the general public. These applications enable computers to perform all or a significant part of the symbolic and numeric calculations present in many mathematical algorithms. The authors use the computer algebra system Wolfram *Mathematica* to implement analytical operator theory algorithms. In [14], it is presented an algorithm that factorize special classes of rational and non-rational matrix functions. These classes are closely related to the solution of the non-linear Schrödinger equation, the generalized Riemann-Hilbert problem, and the study of singular operators that can be represented as a product of Hankel operators [4, 6, 8]. It is shown that for these special classes of matrix functions, a factorization can be obtained using the solutions of two non-homogeneous integral equations. The algorithm was implemented using the Wolfram *Mathematica*, and computes explicit factorizations for those classes of matrix functions using an inner-outer factorization of a component of a factorable matrix function. Regarding computer implementation, complete and explicit rational factorization algorithms (for both scalar and matrix cases) can be found in [15]. However, the algorithms assumes that the given rational function, defined on the unit circle, is factorable and that its zeros and poles are known to the user. Using algorithms described in the [16], which enable the identification of polynomial roots and their location relative to the unit circle, several improvements have been made to the design and implementation of complete factorization algorithms for scalar rational functions, defined

in the unit circle. This article presents an enhanced and highly efficient version of the scalar factorization algorithm described in [15], known as the `[ARFact]2.0` algorithm. This algorithm determines whether a rational function defined on the unit circle is factorable and, if so, identifies its factorization index, even for polynomials of the fifth degree or higher. Designed with the `Root` object concept of the Wolfram Mathematica computer algebra system (to represent solutions of one-variable algebraic equations), `[ARFact]2.0` also provides the explicit factors of a rational factorization. This improved version was made possible by the development of the `[ASPPlusPMinus]` algorithm [16], which calculates the projections associated with the Cauchy-type singular integral defined on the unit circle. The article also presents the new `[AInnerOuterFact]` algorithm, which determines whether a rational function is analytic inside the unit circle and, if so, provides an explicit inner-outer factorization. This can be used to enhance algorithms such as the one described in [14]. The outputs from these algorithms can be used to create or improve various other operator theory algorithms.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 covers fundamental concepts related to rational function factorization and the Cauchy-type singular integral operators used. It also provides a brief description of the operator theory algorithms `[AZeros]` and `[APoles]`, which compute the zeros and poles of a rational function and determine their location relative to the unit circle [16]. Section 3 introduces the new `[ARFact]2.0` and `[AInnerOuterFact]` algorithms, which integrate the `[AZeros]` and `[APoles]` algorithms. The final section offers some concluding remarks.

2 FUNDAMENTAL NOTATIONS, CONCEPTS AND AUXILIARY ALGORITHMS

This section contains the fundamental notations and concepts related to the new operator theory algorithms presented in subsections 3.1 and 3.2. It also provides a brief description of the auxiliary operator theory algorithms `[AZeros]` and `[APoles]`.

2.1 Singular integral Operator with Cauchy kernel

Let \mathbb{T} represent the unit circle in the complex plane. Define \mathbb{T}_+ as the open unit disk and \mathbb{T}_- as the exterior region of the unit circle (∞ included). Let $\mathcal{R}(\mathbb{T})$ denote the algebra of rational functions without poles on \mathbb{T} and let $\mathcal{R}_\pm(\mathbb{T})$ be the subsets of $\mathcal{R}(\mathbb{T})$ whose elements have no poles in \mathbb{T}_\pm , respectively.

It is well known that the singular integral operator with Cauchy kernel, $S_{\mathbb{T}}$, defined almost everywhere on \mathbb{T} , by

$$S_{\mathbb{T}}\varphi(t) = \frac{1}{\pi i} \int_{\mathbb{T}} \frac{\varphi(\tau)}{\tau - t} d\tau, \quad t \in \mathbb{T}, \quad (1)$$

where the integral is understood in the sense of its principal value, is a bounded linear operator in the Lebesgue space $L_2(\mathbb{T})$. In addition, $S_{\mathbb{T}}$ is a unitary and selfadjoint operator in $L_2(\mathbb{T})$. Thus, we can associate with $S_{\mathbb{T}}$ the two complementary Cauchy

projection operators

$$P_{\pm} = (I \pm S_{\mathbb{T}})/2, \quad (2)$$

where I represents the identity operator.

The projection operators (2) allow us to decompose the algebra $\mathcal{R}(\mathbb{T})$ in the topological direct sum

$$\mathcal{R}(\mathbb{T}) = \mathcal{R}_+(\mathbb{T}) \oplus \mathcal{R}_-^0(\mathbb{T}), \quad (3)$$

where $\mathcal{R}_+(\mathbb{T}) = P_+\mathcal{R}(\mathbb{T})$ and $\mathcal{R}_-^0(\mathbb{T}) = P_-\mathcal{R}(\mathbb{T})$. We also have $\mathcal{R}_-(\mathbb{T}) = \mathcal{R}_-^0(\mathbb{T}) \oplus \mathbb{C}$.

2.2 Rational function factorization

This subsection is dedicated to factorization concepts applied to rational functions r , from the traditional (for $r \in \mathcal{R}(\mathbb{T})$) and the inner-outer decomposition perspectives (for $r \in \mathcal{R}_+(\mathbb{T})$).

The success of obtaining a factorization of a rational function r , defined in the unit circle, depends on the possibility of finding zeros and poles by solving polynomial equations. Additionally, it is crucial to determine their locations relative to the curve where the function is defined. This task becomes particularly challenging when dealing with polynomials of the fifth degree or higher.

2.2.1 Scalar rational factorization

In this subsection it is considered the traditional rational factorization concept.

Definition 1 *Let $r \in \mathcal{R}(\mathbb{T})$. A decomposition*

$$r(t) = r_+(t)t^{\kappa}r_-(t), \quad (4)$$

where $r_+, 1/r_+ \in \mathcal{R}_+(\mathbb{T})$, $r_-, 1/r_- \in \mathcal{R}_-(\mathbb{T})$, and $\kappa \in \mathbb{Z}$, is called a scalar rational factorization of the function r with respect to the curve \mathbb{T} . κ is called the factorization index of the rational function r .

The integer κ is uniquely determined by the function r .

If $\kappa = 0$, then r is said to admit a *scalar rational canonical factorization*.

Any function $r \in \mathcal{R}(\mathbb{T})$, without zeros in \mathbb{T} , admits scalar rational factorizations with respect to the curve \mathbb{T} .

2.2.2 Inner-outer rational factorization

In this subsection it is considered another factorization concept, applied to rational functions without poles in the unit disk.

Definition 2 Let $r \in \mathcal{R}_+(\mathbb{T})$. A decomposition

$$r(t) = \theta(t)out(t), \tag{5}$$

where $\theta(t)$ is an inner function and $out(t)$ is an outer function, is called an inner-outer rational factorization of the function r with respect to the curve \mathbb{T} .

Obviously, in the rational case, θ is a Blaschke product and $out(t)$ does not have zeros in $\mathbb{T} \cup \mathbb{T}_+$.

Any function $r \in \mathcal{R}_+(\mathbb{T})$, without zeros in \mathbb{T} , admits an inner-outer rational factorization with respect to the curve \mathbb{T} .

2.3 [AZeros] and [APoles] algorithms

This subsection is dedicated to a brief description of the [AZeros] and [APoles] algorithms, designed and implemented by the authors [16]. Even in cases when polynomials of the fifth degree or higher are considered, the symbolic and numeric capabilities of Wolfram *Mathematica*¹ allow us to determine the zeros and the poles of a scalar rational function, and to identify their location relative to \mathbb{T} , \mathbb{T}_+ , and \mathbb{T}_- .

Furthermore, the [AZeros] and [APoles] algorithms were created to be used as part of other more complex operator theory algorithms and to explore a list of values entered by the user. These algorithms can also be used independently through a *nb* format file where a rational function is input and the Mathematica's *Solve* command is used.

3 NEW OPERATOR THEORY ALGORITHMS

This section is dedicated to the description of new operator theory algorithms.

Subsection 3.1 is dedicated to the improved version of the scalar rational function factorization algorithm presented in [15], the [ARFact]_{2.0} algorithm. The [AInnerOuterFact] algorithm described in Subsection 3.2, after validating the inserted rational function, gives an inner-outer factorization through an output of a Blaschke product and a rational function without zeros and poles in \mathbb{T}_+ .

3.1 [ARFact]_{2.0} Algorithm

This subsection is dedicated to the formal description of the [ARFact]_{2.0} algorithm, which analyzes the factorability of a given rational function and calculates a scalar factorization²

¹*Mathematica* uses the `Root` object concept to represent the solutions of a polynomial equation.

² z_i^\pm ($i = 1, \dots, m_\pm$) denote all the zeros of the function r in \mathbb{T}_\pm (with regard to their multiplicities); p_j^\pm ($j = 1, \dots, n_\pm$) denote all the poles of the function r in \mathbb{T}_\pm (with regard to their multiplicities).

(4) for the given factorable rational functions

$$r_+(t) = \lambda \frac{\prod_{i=1}^{m_-} (t - z_i^-)}{\prod_{j=1}^{n_-} (t - p_j^-)}, \quad r_-(t) = \frac{\prod_{i=1}^{m_+} (1 - t^{-1} z_i^+)}{\prod_{j=1}^{n_+} (1 - t^{-1} p_j^+)}, \quad \kappa = m_+ - n_+, \quad \lambda \in \mathbb{C}. \quad (6)$$

The algorithm allows two input options for the rational function (Figure 1).

```
option =
DialogInput[
DialogNotebook[
{Row[{DefaultButton["Insert r(t) directly.", DialogReturn[opt = 1]],
CancelButton["Insert zeros, poles and λ.", DialogReturn[opt = 2]]}]}];
```


Figure 1: Part of the code structure of the [ARFact]_{2.0} algorithm responsible for the input options for the rational function r .

If *Option 1* is chosen, a new box appears for entering the rational function. If *Option 2* is chosen, new boxes appear for indicating the constant λ and the existing number of zeros and poles (with reference to the multiplicity of each element).

With the integration of the [AZeros] and the [APoles] algorithms (Figure 2), it is possible to validate the input rational function r . Incorrect outputs that could occur with the algorithm presented in [15] (since, in that case, the responsibility for entering a valid factorable function falls on the user) are no longer possible to happen in this improved version.

```
<<"AZeros.m";

<<"APoles.m";

If[circlez ≠ 0, Print["r(t)=",r[t]," is not a factorable function."],
If[circlep≠0, Print["r(t)=",r[t]," ∉ R(T)"],
```

Figure 2: Part of the code structure of the [ARFact]_{2.0} algorithm responsible for the integration of the [AZeros] and [APoles] algorithms, to validate the input rational function r .

The computation of the index of r and the factors r_+ and r_- of a factorization (4) is always possible using data obtained with algorithms applied to specific expressions.

Figure 3 contains the flowchart of the [ARFact]_{2.0} algorithm.

 Figure 3: Flowchart of the [ARFact]_{2.0} algorithm.

3.2 [AInnerOuterFact] Algorithm

This subsection is dedicated to the description of the [AInnerOuterFact] algorithm, which analyzes the factorability of a given rational function and computes an explicit inner-outer factorization (5) for the given factorable rational function $r \in \mathcal{R}_+(\mathbb{T})$, where³

$$\theta(t) = t^q \prod_{k=1}^m \frac{|z_k|}{z_k} \frac{z_k - t}{1 - \overline{z_k}t} \quad (7)$$

and

$$out(t) = \frac{r(t)}{\theta(t)}. \quad (8)$$

³ z_k ($k = 1, \dots, m$) denote all the zeros of r in \mathbb{T}_+ .

This algorithm also allows two input options for the rational function r (Figure 4).

```
DialogInput[{Row[{Button["Insert r(t) directly.",DialogReturn[opt=1]],
Button["Insert zeros, poles with multiplicities and  $\lambda$ .",DialogReturn[opt=2]}]}];
```


Figure 4: Part of the code structure of the [AInnerOuterFact] algorithm responsible for the input options for the rational function r .

The [AInnerOuterFact] algorithm uses [AZeros] and the [APoles] algorithms to validate the input rational function r (Figure 5).

```
<<"AZeros.m";

<<"APoles.m";

If[circlep!=0,Print["r(t)=",r[t],"  $\notin$   $R(\mathbb{T})$ , so is not an inner-outer factorable function."],
If[diskp!= 0,Print["r(t)=",r[t],"  $\notin$   $!\!(\!(+SubscriptBox[\!(R\!), \!(+\!)]\!) (\mathbb{T})$ ,
so is not an inner-outer factorable function."],
If[circlez!= 0,Print["1/r(t)  $\notin$   $R(\mathbb{T})$ , so r is not an inner-outer factorable function."],
```

Figure 5: Part of the code structure of the [AInnerOuterFact] algorithm responsible for the integration of the [AZeros] and [APoles] algorithms, to validate the input rational function r .

The computation of the factors θ and out , for a factorization (5) result from the implementation of the formula (Figure 6).

```
m=Length[listzdisk];If[listzdisk=={ },inner[t]=t^l,
inner[t_]=Product[t^l*Abs[listzdisk[[k]]]/listzdisk[[k]]*
(listzdisk[[k]]-t)/(1-Conjugate[listzdisk[[k]]*t),{k,1,m}];
out[t_]=Simplify[r[t]/inner[t];
```

Figure 6: Part of the code structure of the [AInnerOuterFact] algorithm responsible for the computation of the factors θ and out .

Figure 7 contains the flowchart of the [AInnerOuterFact] algorithm.

4 FINAL REMARKS

The design and implementation of analytical operator theory algorithms can constitute a very interesting line of research.

The authors believe that the methods described in this article can be extended to other operator theory problems, at least in the rational case.

Figure 7: Flowchart of the [AInnerOuterFact] algorithm.

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